

MENTAL DISORDER - AN AWARENESS AMONG TEACHERS: A REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to map the literature on teachers' conceptual understanding and attitude towards mental disorder in students using metadata extracted from International and National Research articles as well as several articles from Journals of International and National editions indexed in the database. More specifically, this study uses scoping reviews to summarize the existing literature regarding the awareness and conceptual understanding of teachers towards children's mental health and their attitude towards those children who are suffering from mental disorders. The review paper also explores different instructional modules provided to train the teachers in the literature and their prevalence in identifying the diseases. It further investigates the causes of mental health concerns in children, what gaps exist in this context of the study, what interventions can be used to address them, and the barriers to identifying the mentally disabled and caring for them. This review aims to improve researchers' understanding of the studies conducted in children's mental health, identify research gaps, and propose evidence-based justification to summarize the need for research in the same area.

Keywords: *Conceptual Understanding, Mental Health, Attitude, Intervention*

Introduction:

Mental health is the successful performance of a cognitive function, resulting in productive activities, fulfilling relationships, and the ability to adapt to change and cope with adversity. In contrast, Mental disorders are medical conditions that disrupt a person's thinking, feeling, mood, ability to relate to others, and daily functioning, resulting in a diminished capacity to cope with the ordinary demands of life.

Today's children are tomorrow's responsible citizens of the world.

Nearly 35 to 45 percent constitutes the young children of the whole world's population.

The future of our country depends on the health of young people.

A child's mental health regarding identifying signs by the teachers can be considered the most neglected area of psychiatry. However, one in 10 children and adolescents have medical problems, below-average intelligence, specific learning disorders, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, emotional issues, poor sociocultural home environment, and psychiatric disorders. Management of mental disorders in children starts from recognizing the needy student, supporting them, guiding them in the right direction, ensuring that they take regular treatment, and continuing regular follow-up and rehabilitating them back into society.

Objectives

For the present study, the investigator thought of the following objectives

1. To enrich the understanding of the topic undertaken by the researcher.
2. Finding gaps in the research conducted on the similar topic
3. To justify the researcher's claim.

Research Questions:

1. How is conceptual understanding and awareness about mental disorders significant for school teachers?
2. What are the gaps in the research that can be identified from the review of related research literature for future researchers?
3. How effective is the training program tried out by earlier researchers on the teaching faculty?

Areas Of Research:

- International Research articles
- Indian research Articles
- Journal Articles

Categories Of Research Review:

- Conceptual understanding of mental disorders.
- The attitude of teachers towards students who have a mental disorder.
- Effectiveness of training program on the capacity building of teachers to identify mental disorders.

1. Conceptual understanding of mental disorders

International Research Articles

Vellutino et al. (1990) conducted a study to assess the progress of children with a reading disability and asked teachers of 1407 children from 17 schools in the Albany area of New York to rate their reading skills in the middle of 1st grade. The teachers were not able to place the students correctly.

Colin HJ, Cynthia W (2008) conducted a study in England. Teachers were provided with a checklist data on a sample of 320 boys and 118 girls who have previously been referred to school psychological services, and a further 183 boys and 39 girls had not been referred. Subjects were aged 5-11 years; there was a high agreement between referred and non - student status and subsequent classification using the child behavioral checklist.

Meltzer I et al. (2006) conducted a study in Switzerland among the 663 students and their 57 teachers to detect teacher's perceptions of the student's strategy use and performance in nine domains. Findings indicated that the students with learning disabilities considered themselves appropriately strategic and competent in the five domains of reading, writing, spelling, math, and organization. These students also rated their academic performance and organization as average to above average in seven of nine domains. The self-rating of students with learning disabilities was still significantly lower than the self-rating of average achievers in virtually all domains. The findings also revealed a sharp discrepancy between the students' self-assessment with a learning disability and their teachers. Teachers rated the students with learning disabilities as weak in their strategy use and below average in their performance in all nine and organizational domains. These results added to the increasing body of literature indicating the efficiency of teachers in accurately identifying cases and learning disabled children's perception as capable and effective.

Taylor HG et al. (2002) conducted a study in India stating the efficiency of kindergarten teacher judgment in identifying early learning problems. To identify early learning problems, kindergarten teachers in a suburban school rated student progress towards six academic objectives as satisfactory or unsatisfactory. 20% of the district's 303 kindergarten children received terrible ratings in at least one area—thirty-eight of these children (identified group). Results of testing conducted revealed poorer academic achievement in identified children than in non - identified children. Children

from the specified group also performed more poorly than children from a non-identified group on tests of phonological processing and working memory/executive functioning. They were rated by teachers as having more behavior and attention problems and lower social competence. Follow-up of the cases to the first grade documented ongoing learning issues in the identified group. These findings support teacher judgment in the early detection of learning problems and found that the result is unsatisfactory.

Lack of knowledge about psychiatric illnesses is widely prevalent outside India, too. A study done in the Nigerian community revealed an equal lack of scientific understanding regarding mental illness.

Oye G, Benjamin OO, Lola C. Community study of knowledge of and attitude to mental illness in Nigeria. *Br J Psychiatry* 2005;186:436-41. Back to cited text no. 17

Indian Research Articles

Soman SK (2004) conducted a study in Hyderabad regarding teachers' knowledge regarding the behavioral problems of children. The sample consisted of 45 teachers aged between 25-51 years from seven schools, and it was found that only 4 % of the teachers have conceptual knowledge of mental illness.

Liza Thank Daniel, Sandhya Gupta Liza, and Rajesh Sagar's (2003) study reported a significant increase in primary school teachers' knowledge regarding early symptoms of childhood psychiatric disorders after exposure to the self-instruction module. This finding was that self-instruction in their study on childhood psychiatric disorders could improve teachers' knowledge. In the present study, teachers' knowledge score was high among primary school teachers teaching in government and among those who had attended in-and programs in the past. Whereas, after the intervention, primary school teachers from private schools gained more knowledge than other types of school, it might be due to their felt need to learn more about childhood psychiatric disorders. Most of the primary school teachers (74%) in the present study had learned about childhood psychiatric disorders during their teachers' training. How Learned Their knowledge score was not significantly different from those who did not study these topics during their training. The possible reason could be that, though teachers learn introductory general psychology at the pre-service level, they do not receive specific training to identify a wide variety of symptoms related to childhood psychiatric disorders.

A study conducted on the Indian teacher community before their training observed that as few as 22% could recognize depression, and even fewer (9.1%) could recognize psychosis.

Gregory A, Mitchell K, Shoba R, Sujatha SC, Anthony FJ. A mental health training program for community health workers in India: Impact on knowledge and attitudes. *Int J Ment Health Syst* 2011;5:1-6. Back to cited text no. 15

Journal Articles

National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (2005) states in a longitudinal interventional study, since, 1985 over 12 years on 34501 children in 11 states in the USA and Canada to identify early intervention and remediation measures for children with a learning problem. This study explained the significance of teachers in the management of such children.

BMC psychiatry, part of Springer Nature, 16th November 2000, stated that India is home to a third of the world's youth. Mental health problems are likely to impact the productivity and capabilities of India's youth adversely. Among youth included in this review, one-third had poor knowledge and negative attitudes, and one-fifth intended to or had discriminated against a person with mental illness. Although most of these studies were among college students, they were predominantly focused on health professionals in training and teachers. Educational interventions to reduce the stigma associated with mental health may improve help-seeking behaviors by avoiding the use of psychiatric labels that are not commonly understood, instead focus on symptomatic vignettes that may explicitly discuss a range of mental health problems with varying severity. Intervention content that directly and interactively discusses youth mental-health-stigma-related responses and age-appropriate social roles, rather than focusing on future roles such as marriage, may help to achieve timely detection of mental health disorders among youth. The knowledge and awareness of the concept of mental health and behavioral issues will help the child development and human development as a whole.

International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 3, Issue 2, February 2013 1, Mental disorders are seen to vary across time, within the same populations at the same time. The dynamic nature of the psychiatric illness impacts its planning, funding, and healthcare delivery. Various studies have shown that mental disorders are high in the female gender, child and adolescent population, students,

elderly population, people suffering from chronic medical conditions, disabled population, disaster survivors, and industrial workers. Community surveys related to this context and awareness have the advantage of being more representative.

Interpretation of category 1

Based on the reviewed literature, it is significant that the conceptual knowledge of teachers related to Mental disorders is low, and teachers confuse mental illness with mischief. Increasing awareness in this aspect will help to manage children's behavior

2. The Attitude of Teachers towards Students who have a Mental Disorder.

International Research Articles

Osmanaga (2013) found that Teachers' attitudes regarding inclusive education in China impacted pupils' attitudes towards their disabled peers.

Boer, Pijl & Minnaert (2011) concluded in a study conducted in Austria that the majority of teachers seem to hold undecided or negative attitudes towards inclusive education.

Yola Center & James Ward conducted a survey to explore teachers' and principals' attitudes related to inclusion. Regular and resource teachers from New South Wales government and nongovernment schools were surveyed to elicit their attitudes towards the integration of individual disabled children, the support services currently provided and the skills considered essential for teachers of mainstreamed atypical students. Differences among subgroups of teachers and between teachers and principals who had completed the same questionnaire in a previous study were also examined. Results indicate that teachers' attitudes to the integration of individual disabled children reflect a lack of confidence both in their own instructional skills and in the quality of support personnel currently provided to them. They are positive about integrating only those children whose disabling characteristics are not likely to require extra instructional or management skills on the part of the teacher. However, teachers' attitudes may be significantly modified by their pre-service training and the nature of their subsequent professional experience. Examination of the skills needed by mainstreaming staff reveals that, while general competence is considered essential, neither regular nor resource teachers seem aware of the need for a structured approach to curriculum objectives. The finding that principals' attitudes are consistently more positively than those expressed by teachers suggests a somewhat unrealistic perception by the former of teachers' current anxieties about integration.

Bruno J. D'Alonzo, Gerard Giordano & Tracy L. Cross (2016) in their recent year's research reform and arguments (pro and con) in special education have focused on including all students with disabilities in general education settings. This movement toward the "inclusion" of all students with disabilities is a controversial one, with its share of proponents and opponents; each group emphasizing the fact that the current dual system of education (general education and special education) is faulty and is failing in its purpose to educate students in the least restrictive environment. Regardless of whether or not school districts or states adopt policies on the inclusion of all students with disabilities, the fact remains that to date not all teachers within the public school systems have positive attitudes about teaching students with disabilities or are trained or educated to do so. The authors of this article address the contention that in order to improve, change, or even illuminate teachers' negative perceptions about including students with disabilities, the training of all teachers needs to take place.

National Research Articles

Payal & Mayaan (2015) aimed at studying the attitude of teachers towards inclusive education. A semi-structured self-constructed interview schedule and a self-constructed attitude scale were used to study the attitude of teachers towards students with disabilities and Inclusive education, and results revealed that teachers had some amount of awareness, but their attitude towards children with disabilities was inadequate.

Belapukar, Phatak & Uplane (2011) examined the knowledge and attitude of school teachers of urban and rural schools of India. The results indicated a positive attitude of school teachers towards inclusive education, and the knowledge level of school teachers about mental disabilities is found to be significantly low.

- Journal articles

In an article in the Mushoriwa Journal by Glauban & Lifshitz (2001), it was reported that the majority of teachers (86 percent) in San Antonio were unwilling to include pupils with special needs in their classroom.

Interpretation of category 2

In several research reviews of the literature, all teachers have been uniformly observed to possess substantial negativity toward students with mental disorders and their inclusion.

Researchers found that in the nursing profession, the feeling and attitude were more positive than in the teaching profession.

3. Effectiveness of Training Program on the Capacity Building of Teachers to Identify Mental Disorders.

International Research Articles

Johanna Wyn (2009) conducted a program that was piloted in 24 secondary schools drawn from states of Australia to develop Mind matters. A team of academics and health educator professionals amended the pilot run. They concluded that teachers need to be trained comfortable and confident in promoting and teaching for mental health. the training and support of the teachers help in the effective and efficient improvement even in chronic mental disorders.

National Research Articles

Vijayalakshmi N, Benitta(2017) researched the effect of self-instructional modules on knowledge and attitude regarding the prevention of obesity among adolescents. The study assesses the effectiveness of self-instructional modules on knowledge and attitude regarding the prevention of obesity among adolescents in a selected school, Coimbatore. The researchers concluded that the self-instructional Module effectively improves the expertise and mood regarding preventing obesity among adolescents.

Crowe E. (2016) conducted research on teaching critical reflection skills for advanced mental health nursing practice., a constructive -reconstructive approach. The nursing literature reviewed was accessed through the Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL). It was concluded that the deconstructive–reconstructive approach to the development of critical thinking skills provides the advanced practitioners with the opportunity to integrate practice, theory, and research.

Journal Articles

The Indian Psychiatry Journal Edition 2016 Jun-Dec stated that earlier strategies to enhance mental health have not succeeded over the past six decades or more in less-developed countries. It is time now to take on a new approach with renewed vigor. Mental health awareness can become both the means and the way of ending this apathy. Progressive government policies based on evidence-based practices, and engaged media, a vibrant educational system, teachers with awareness of the disorders, a responsive industry, aggressive utilization of newer technologies, and creative crowd-sourcing might together help dispel the blight of mental illnesses.

In an article in an International Journal of The University of Western Ontario on "Identifying and supporting students with mental health challenges," it was found that the number of children and youth struggling with mental health challenges is prevalent. The teachers have an influential role in students' lives and learning, and teachers require professional development training regarding student mental health issues.

Interpretation of category 3

The reviews related to the effectiveness of teachers' training programs to enhance their knowledge and attitude towards mental disorders are considerably less in number. However, the articles and research found are reviewed to show that most teachers, who were not currently participating in inclusive programs, had strong, negative feelings about inclusion. Those who had undergone training programs developed positive attitudes towards disabilities and inclusion.

Overall Conclusion

The findings were that teachers' conceptual knowledge and attitudes towards students with mental disorders were consistently more positive after undergoing training programs than those teachers who were never exposed to any training.

The research on training programs for pre-service and in-service teachers for the capacity building to accommodate, identify, and help the children be treated since childhood is the most critical and neglected area of educational research. This is considered as the gap in the research area related to mental disorders.

Implications of these findings will help the researcher conduct research in a similar area to fill the gaps identified and improve teachers' attitudes through instructional Modules in developing awareness towards identifying the disabilities and the inclusion of students with disabilities into their classroom.

Justification for the research

Thus, based on the reviews of the related literature, the researcher would like to research a similar area to reduce the gaps and increase the teachers' conceptual understanding to diagnose the mental disorders in the children to start the remedial measures and interventions.

The researcher plans to create a Self-instructional Module to train the teachers to identify a few common mental disorders.

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